

Kinaesthetic Traffic Characterization and Performance Trade-Offs in Haptic Teleoperation Systems over 5G Standalone Private Networks

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Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive characterization of kinaesthetic data traffic and associated performance trade-offs in multimodal bilateral haptic teleoperation over 5G networks. Utilizing two widely adopted haptic devices interacting with virtual environments, precise telemetry on motion and force was obtained across various interaction types and virtual object properties. The study investigates the effects of network resource allocation within a 5G standalone private network by employing three predefined network slicing profiles prioritizing haptic, audio, or video traffic. Performance evaluations were conducted using Quality of Service (QoS) metrics, from which potential implications for Quality of Experience (QoE) were subsequently inferred. The results show the interplay between traffic patterns and resource allocation, identifying configurations that ensure high-fidelity haptic feedback while maintaining acceptable audiovisual quality. These insights lay the groundwork for future research on adaptive network management strategies for haptic-enabled teleoperation systems.

Index Terms—Haptic Teleoperation, Multimodal Communication, Network Slice, Traffic Characterization, Immersive QoE

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of bilateral teleoperation systems with haptic feedback has significantly enhanced applications in remote robotics [1], telemedicine [2], and immersive environments [3] by enabling precise kinaesthetic feedback. These systems rely on multimodal communication [4] combining haptic, audio, and video streams to deliver seamless remote interaction. However, stringent requirements for haptic feedback—high packet rates, low latency, and minimal jitter—pose significant challenges [5], particularly when deployed over shared networks with competing traffic demands. These challenges are further amplified by the perceptual encoding schemes such as IEEE 1918.1.1-2024, which produce irregular, interaction-dependent packet streams rather than constant-rate data flows.

Fig. 1. Different interaction modes, different physical properties.

This work addresses the complexities of characterizing kinaesthetic data traffic and analyzing the trade-offs inherent in dynamically allocating network resources across multimodal feedback streams. Leveraging commonly used haptic interfaces (Novint’s Falcon and 3D System’s Touch device), we developed an autonomous measurement system that systematically interacts with virtual environments characterized by varying physical parameters, including stiffness, friction coefficients, and viscosity. The system enables precise monitoring of position, orientation, linear and angular velocity, as well as applied force and torque, on three-dimensional axes. Various interaction modes shown in Figure 1, including tapping, holding, dragging, and shearing, are analyzed in controlled slow / fast movement scenarios, providing information on dynamics of haptic communications.

Based on this characterization, we evaluated the performance of these systems in a 5G network slicing context [6], using the UPV 5G Standalone Private Network [7]. This network provides extensive configurability, including adjustable

Fig. 2. Measuring system architecture for experimental bilateral haptic teleoperation, encompassing Operator, Network and Teleoperator Domains.

5G Quality of Service Identifier (5QI) profiles, Time Division Duplex (TDD) patterns, and subcarrier spacing, to optimize resource allocation for multimodal traffic. Specifically, we investigate the impact of prioritizing haptic traffic by reallocating resources from audio and video slices and assess how these changes influence the overall QoS.

The primary contributions of this study include: (1) a detailed methodology for kinaesthetic traffic characterization under dynamic virtual object interactions, (2) a quantitative evaluation of trade-offs in resource allocation for multimodal systems, and (3) experimental insights into the interplay between haptic feedback quality and multimodal QoS in a 5G-enabled network environment. This work sets the stage for developing adaptive resource allocation mechanisms tailored to the unique demands of haptic teleoperation systems.

II. RELATED WORK

Recent advancements in haptic teleoperation systems have focused on enhancing control intuitiveness and feedback precision. For instance, a study by University of Leuven [8] introduced an intuitive teleoperation system utilizing a Geomagic Touch haptic interface to control a 6-DoF robotic manipulator, emphasizing the integration of virtual and physical sensor-induced haptic feedback to improve environmental awareness and operational safety. In the realm of network optimization [9], the concept of 5G network slicing has been explored to allocate dedicated network resources for specific applications, including haptic communications. A report by 5G Americas [10] discusses the potential of network slicing to monetize 5G investments by creating isolated logical networks tailored to distinct service requirements. Despite these developments, comprehensive haptic traffic analyses under real-world network slicing conditions are scarce [11]. This research builds upon recent IEEE 1918.1 standardization efforts [12] by providing an in-depth analysis of haptic traffic patterns

and examining trade-offs in network resource allocation for multimodal teleoperation scenarios.

Recent advancements in the Tactile Internet have focused on intelligent, adaptive resource management, particularly through AI-driven RAN slicing techniques. Notably, Kokkinis et al. proposed a Deep Reinforcement Learning-based framework for video-haptic RAN slicing that dynamically balances radio resources between haptic (URLLC) and video (eMBB) streams, achieving up to a 25% increase in user satisfaction compared to static slicing in simulation studies [13]. Ericsson’s 2024 field report underscores the value of true 5G Standalone (SA) deployments—including network slicing—for latency-critical applications such as telesurgery, enabling end-to-end delays at roughly twice the theoretical minimum compared to five times under best-effort Internet [14]. In the context of multi-service RAN slicing, Nagib et al. demonstrated a hybrid transfer-learning enhanced DRL approach in O-RAN controllers that significantly improved convergence speed and stability across heterogeneous services, including real VR-gaming traffic, achieving gains of +7.7% in initial reward and -64% variance [15]. While these works illustrate the potential of simulated RAN strategies, our study is unique in empirically characterizing real kinaesthetic traffic and quantifying its interaction with slicing mechanisms on a physical 5G SA private network, bridging the gap between theoretical frameworks and real-world, system-level evaluations.

III. MEASURING SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system architecture interchangeably uses two kinaesthetic haptic devices—a Novint Falcon and a 3D Systems Touch—to facilitate precise motion tracking and interaction with virtual environments. This system is designed to autonomously execute predefined movements while capturing real-time telemetry data, enabling a comprehensive analysis of haptic communication dynamics under varying interaction conditions. The architecture, depicted in Figure 2, consists

of three main components: the haptic operator domain, the network domain, and the processing teleoperator domain.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF FALCON AND TOUCH DEVICE CAPABILITIES

	Novint Falcon	3D Systems Touch
Degrees of Freedom	3 DoF positional sensing and 3 DoF force feedback	6 DoF positional sensing and 3 DoF force feedback
Max Force Output	9.0 N	3.3 N
Spatial Resolution	0.03 mm	0.055 mm
Update Rate	1 kHz	1 kHz
Workspace Dims.	10 × 10 × 10 cm	16 × 12 × 7 cm
Application Suitability	High-force interactions, rigid object simulation	Precision-based interactions, surface exploration

A. System Overview

The haptic input layer comprises the Falcon or Touch devices, providing different degrees of freedom in positional sensing, with additional force feedback capabilities, shown in Table I. The Falcon, a parallel manipulator, enables high-fidelity force rendering, making it suitable for simulating contact with rigid objects, while the Touch device offers enhanced precision for surface interactions and free-space movements. Using the *chai3D* library [16] compatible with both devices, the teleoperation and control module synchronizes motion execution, records telemetry (position, velocity, applied force/torque) and processes interactions with virtual objects characterized by distinct material properties such as stiffness, static and dynamic friction, and viscosity.

The networked feedback system is responsible for encoding, transmitting, and receiving haptic data packets via a communication protocol compliant with the kinaesthetic no-delay codec (KCnD) profile, typically captured with at least 1kHz, which undergo perceptual data reduction leading to irregular updates sent in packets, as outlined in IEEE 1918.1-2024 standard. The system operates in a bilateral teleoperation framework, where force and motion signals are exchanged bidirectionally between the client (haptic input) and server (virtual environment). Telemetry data are transmitted in real-time over a 5G Private Network, which allows controlled variations in network slicing parameters to assess the trade-offs between haptic, audio, and video feedback streams.

B. Motion Execution and Interaction

The system supports both autonomous motion execution and user-driven interaction to evaluate haptic traffic patterns across different conditions. Autonomous trajectories are pre-programmed to ensure repeatability, with movement sequences covering a range of interaction types, including no-contact cycles, tapping or holding on Z-axis, dragging on Y-axis, and shearing (i.e. oblique tapping) on YZ plane. These interactions are performed iteratively at controlled velocities, classified into slow or fast movements using velocities between 0.2 and 0.8 m/s on cycles of 2.5 and 1.0 sec respectively. By systematically

varying environmental parameters across ranges specified in Table II, the system captures the impact of contact dynamics on haptic packet generation.

TABLE II
RANGES AND COEFFICIENTS FOR PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

	VALUE RANGES		FRICTION COEFF.	
	Stiffness (Unit: N/m)	Viscosity (Unit: N·s/m)	Static (adim.)	Dynamic (adim.)
Lower	400	10.0	0.5	0.3
Medium	700	20.0	0.7	0.5
Higher	1000	30.0	1.0	0.7

These specific interaction types were selected based on their relevance to real-world applications. Tapping and holding are commonly encountered in surgical robotics and remote object manipulation, where precise force application is critical. Dragging and shearing motions are representative of industrial and telemaintenance tasks, where frictional resistance must be taken into account in tool operation. No-contact cycles provide a baseline for comparison, isolating motion-induced packet variations from force-dependent interactions.

IV. TRAFFIC CHARACTERIZATION

The transmission dynamics of haptic feedback in bilateral teleoperation systems exhibit distinct statistical patterns compared to conventional audiovisual data streams. Unlike periodic video frames or continuous audio signals, haptic traffic is event-driven and highly dependent on the interaction modality, user motion, and environmental parameters. Haptic packets are generated asynchronously based on real-time force and position variations. Each transmitted packet encapsulates a fixed payload of 624 bits, comprising a 48-bit header and a 576-bit data field.

An analysis of haptic traffic patterns, illustrated in Figure 3 as well as Tables III and IV, reveals that packet transmission rates remain moderate. No-contact scenarios produce the lowest transmission rates, as packets primarily carry positional updates with minimal force variations. Contact-intensive interactions, such as tapping and holding, exhibit short-lived spikes in packet generation due to abrupt force changes, but do not sustain high transmission rates over extended periods. In contrast, dragging and shearing interactions result in steadier packet rates, particularly when friction and viscosity impose additional resistance, needing continuous corrective force updates.

The mechanical properties of the virtual environment critically influence haptic traffic behavior. These dynamics are directly shaped by the perceptual data reduction scheme outlined in IEEE 1918.1.1-2024, which adaptively modulates packet generation based on changes in force and motion, leading to bursts or suppression of transmissions depending on interaction intensity. Higher stiffness values amplify instantaneous force responses upon contact, increasing packet transmission rates but within controlled limits. Tapping and holding interactions in high-stiffness settings exhibit maximum packet rates that remain below 300 packets per second on

Fig. 3. Packets Transmitted per Percentual Velocity Change (Leader) or Percentual Force Change (Follower) and Packet Rate Distribution over 60 seconds samples for different Interaction Modes and Physical Properties of the Virtual Environment. [St: Stiffness, Fr: Friction, Vi: Viscosity, Sp: Speed]

TABLE III
PACKET RATES PER MOVEMENT INTERACTION AND PHYSICAL PROPERTY ACROSS VALUE RANGES (LOW, MED, HIGH) FOR LEADER/CLIENT

Stiffness	Mean	No-Contact	Tapping	Holding	Dragging	Shearing
	Std Dev	(-, -, -)	(212.2, 255.9, 275.4)	(204.6, 178.6, 171.0)	(13.02, 12.03, 11.58)	(241.3, 259.4, 255.8)
Viscosity	Minimum	(-, -, -)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)
	Maximum	(-, -, -)	(241, 278, 309)	(241, 214, 197)	(269, 305, 295)	(360, 328, 386)
	Mean	(225.9, 178.6, 132.3)	(270.3, 263.5, 152.7)	(200.9, 195.7, 198.4)	(228.6, 237.1, 224.4)	(270.3, 263.5, 152.7)
Friction	Std Dev	(18.81, 24.57, 23.65)	(27.05, 33.23, 27.51)	(14.54, 14.02, 15.60)	(19.59, 20.18, 17.20)	(27.05, 33.23, 27.51)
	Minimum	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)
	Maximum	(249, 224, 168)	(322, 341, 220)	(224, 225, 228)	(264, 267, 253)	(322, 341, 220)
	Mean	(-, -, -)	(295.5, 287.6, 270.0)	(168.6, 168.1, 170.8)	(259.2, 271.3, 273.8)	(235.0, 273.3, 343.6)
Friction	Std Dev	(-, -, -)	(24.34, 24.79, 23.27)	(11.88, 11.79, 12.38)	(23.19, 25.19, 25.55)	(20.76, 29.01, 31.44)
	Minimum	(-, -, -)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)
	Maximum	(-, -, -)	(330, 322, 297)	(200, 203, 217)	(294, 314, 317)	(338, 356, 376)

TABLE IV
PACKET RATES PER MOVEMENT INTERACTION AND PHYSICAL PROPERTY ACROSS VALUE RANGES (LOW, MED, HIGH) FOR FOLLOWER/SERVER

Stiffness	Mean	No-Contact	Tapping	Holding	Dragging	Shearing
	Std Dev	(-, -, -)	(82.47, 71.16, 68.16)	(204.61, 178.65, 171.00)	(13.02, 12.03, 11.58)	(78.93, 76.23, 85.31)
Viscosity	Minimum	(-, -, -)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)
	Maximum	(-, -, -)	(99, 78, 76)	(241, 214, 197)	(97, 97, 104)	(135, 161, 98)
	Mean	(225.9, 178.6, 132.3)	(281.7, 234.5, 147.8)	(132.1, 127.4, 125.1)	(111.7, 108.9, 115.8)	(281.7, 234.5, 147.8)
Friction	Std Dev	(18.81, 24.57, 23.65)	(29.16, 25.39, 28.01)	(8.36, 8.29, 8.60)	(9.47, 9.46, 8.48)	(29.16, 25.39, 28.01)
	Minimum	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)
	Maximum	(249, 224, 168)	(329, 313, 210)	(148, 136, 135)	(129, 123, 133)	(329, 313, 210)
	Mean	(-, -, -)	(67.67, 67.87, 70.30)	(168.56, 168.12, 170.81)	(57.22, 68.05, 76.93)	(62.50, 70.56, 73.78)
Friction	Std Dev	(-, -, -)	(9.09, 9.47, 9.36)	(11.88, 11.79, 12.38)	(5.34, 6.09, 6.24)	(9.90, 20.82, 11.47)
	Minimum	(-, -, -)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.0)
	Maximum	(-, -, -)	(76, 76, 77)	(200, 203, 217)	(93, 88, 98)	(89, 130, 119)

average. Conversely, viscosity introduces a damping effect smoothing out force variations, leading to a more stable yet slightly lower packet rate. Friction coefficients further modulate transmission behavior by dictating the frequency of force adjustments during sustained movement. High static and dynamic friction values require constant force readjustments, leading to packet rates exceeding 250 packets per second.

Peaks in packet transmission seen in Figure 3 correspond to abrupt velocity or force changes, reinforcing the event-driven nature of haptic communication. However, the absolute packet rates remain moderate and well within the capacity of standard teleoperation communication channels. The same figure also demonstrates moderate dispersion in transmission behavior across different interaction modes and environmental settings. High-stiffness, high-friction conditions result in slightly increased packet rate variability, while lower stiffness and viscosity contribute to a more uniform distribution.

Packet rate variability, as indicated by standard deviation values in Tables III and IV, remains within a moderate range of 50 to 100 packets per second. While fluctuations are present, they do not introduce critical latency or bandwidth constraints in multimodal haptic communication. However, to further optimize transmission efficiency, network-aware adaptation techniques can be employed, in order to dynamically adjust encoding granularity based on perceptual relevance, prioritizing essential force updates while reducing redundant transmissions to maintain interaction fidelity.

V. 5G NETWORK CONFIGURATION PROFILES

To systematically evaluate the interplay between network resource allocation and multimodal performance in bilateral teleoperation, three network configuration profiles were designed: Haptic Priority, Balanced, and Best-Effort. Each profile represents a distinct resource allocation strategy within the 5G network slicing framework, modulating QoS parameters to optimize either latency-sensitive haptic feedback or bandwidth-intensive audiovisual streams. These configurations were not selected heuristically but based on measurable trade-offs between delay, jitter tolerance, and throughput sensitivity for each modality. The parameter assignments align with 3GPP recommendations for QoS differentiation (TS 23.501), while also reflecting real-world traffic asymmetries observed in bilateral haptic teleoperation systems. Table V summarizes the key network parameters that were varied in the study.

A. Haptic Priority Profile

The *Haptic Priority* configuration applies ultra-reliable low-latency communication settings, assigning haptic streams to 5QI profiles with millisecond latency targets and guaranteed bit rates. Uplink-dominant TDD patterns (*4:1 UL/DL*) and minimal subcarrier spacing (*15 kHz*) mitigate jitter and ensure temporal precision in force-feedback transmissions. Lower subcarrier spacing reduces inter-symbol interference and enhances synchronization, ensuring stable real-time force feedback. This TDD asymmetry reflects the bidirectional nature of haptic systems, where uplink telemetry is more

TABLE V
CONFIGURABLE NETWORK PARAMETERS

	Description	Network Impact
5QI Profile (from 3GPP TS 23.501)	- 3 (Guaranteed BR, 1 ms latency), - 7 (Non-GBR, 10-30 ms latency), - 9 (Non-GBR, 50-100 ms latency)	Prioritization of traffic, affects latency and jitter
TDD Pattern	UL/DL slot ratio (1:4, 3:7, 4:6)	Determines latency asymmetry
Subcarrier Spacing	15 kHz, 30 kHz, 120 kHz	Balances coverage versus throughput
MIMO Configuration	2x2, 4x4 antenna processing	Enhances spatial multiplexing
Beamforming	Directional optimization (fixed/adaptive)	Improves signal strength and reduces interference
Carrier Aggregation	2, 3, or 4 aggregated carriers	Increases bandwidth and reduces congestion

latency-sensitive than downlink video. A 15 kHz spacing was selected to maximize symbol duration and resilience to timing error in low-mobility indoor deployments. This configuration reallocates bandwidth from audio and video streams, assigned to higher-latency 5QI profiles, resulting in increased packet loss and jitter for these modalities. MIMO 2x2 is maintained to reduce computational overhead on the user equipment while ensuring spatial diversity, and adaptive beamforming is employed to maintain signal fidelity without relying on precomputed directions. It is important to note that the effective MIMO performance also depends on the capabilities of the user device, including antenna configuration, RF front-end quality, and channel conditions.

B. Balanced Profile

The *Balanced* configuration distributes network resources to maintain QoS parity across haptic, audio, and video streams. Moderate 5QI profiles with flexible latency constraints are employed (*7 for haptic, 7 for audio, 9 for video*), combined with symmetrical TDD patterns (*3:7 UL/DL*) and adaptive subcarrier spacing (*30 kHz*). While this approach minimizes severe degradation in any single modality, it introduces tolerable inconsistencies in high-frequency haptic interactions. 5QI 7 ensures predictable non-GBR behavior with tolerable latency (<30 ms) for both haptic and audio flows. A 30 kHz subcarrier spacing strikes a balance between reduced symbol duration (for improved throughput) and acceptable sensitivity to Doppler spread in moderate mobility scenarios. The use of MIMO 4x4 supports spatial multiplexing for simultaneous multimodal flows, and triple carrier aggregation provides sufficient bandwidth without excessive signaling overhead.

C. Best-Effort Profile

Conversely, the *Best-Effort* configuration prioritizes audiovisual throughput by leveraging higher-latency 5QI profiles for haptic streams (*5QI 9*), permitting delays up to 100 ms. Downlink-centric TDD patterns (*1:4 UL/DL*) and expanded subcarrier spacing (*120 kHz*) enhance video and audio performance but induce perceptible delays and force-feedback

inconsistencies, particularly in dynamic haptic tasks. The 5QI 9 profile tolerates high latency and jitter, making it suitable for delay-insensitive streams. A 1:4 TDD pattern favors downlink-heavy workloads, such as HD video rendering. The 120 kHz subcarrier spacing maximizes spectral efficiency and is compatible with high-order modulation schemes under good channel conditions, reducing frame durations. MIMO 4x4 and fixed beamforming configurations are selected to simplify control signaling and maximize throughput stability in static environments.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental evaluation of network resource allocation strategies and their impact on multimodal teleoperation, followed by an analysis of the observed trade-offs and implications for future implementations. Statistical evaluation was performed under controlled conditions with network traffic loads ranging from 50% to 95% of system capacity. Further stress tests were conducted under simulated high-interference environments to evaluate system robustness. Experiments were conducted at varying levels of congestion to assess the resilience of the system and identify thresholds at which performance begins to degrade significantly.

A. Impact on Latency and Jitter

Haptic feedback demands stringent latency requirements. Table VI presents the mean, standard deviation, and worst-case observed latencies across different 5QI profiles. Lower 5QI values resulted in significantly reduced delays, ensuring real-time responsiveness for force feedback. Jitter variations were minimized under uplink-heavy TDD patterns, further stabilizing haptic transmission. Furthermore, Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of latency and jitter measurements, highlighting the variance between different configurations. While the Haptic Priority setting ensures low-latency force feedback, the Best-Effort configuration results in large delays, which introduce perceptible inconsistencies in real-time interactions.

Fig. 4. Latency and Jitter distributions across different network configurations.

B. Trade-offs in Audio and Video Quality

Prioritizing haptic data resulted in increased packet loss and latency for audio and video streams using AAC (≈ 300 bytes per packet at 20 packets per second) and H264 codifications (≈ 1500 bytes per packet at 30 packet per second). Higher subcarrier spacing improved overall throughput but introduced

TABLE VI
NETWORK RESULTS ACROSS NETWORK CONFIGURATIONS

	LATENCY			JITTER	
	Mean	Std Dev	Max	Mean	Max
Haptic Priority	4.2 ms	0.8 ms	6.5 ms	0.5 ms	1.2 ms
Balanced	7.9 ms	1.2 ms	11.3 ms	1.0 ms	2.5 ms
Best-Effort	15.4 ms	3.1 ms	23.7 ms	3.0 ms	6.8 ms

video frame drops under high-load conditions. In this regard, Table VII presents the measured packet loss percentages and QoE impact for different configurations.

TABLE VII
PACKET LOSS & QOE IMPACT ACROSS NETWORK CONFIGURATIONS

	PACKET LOSS (%)			QoE Impact
	Haptic	Audio	Video	
Haptic Priority	0.5 - 1.2	4.8 - 6.3	7.1 - 9.2	Degraded Audio-Visual quality. Haptic transmission with minimal distortions.
Balanced	0.8 - 1.5	2.0 - 3.1	3.8 - 5.2	Controlled packet loss across all streams.
Best-Effort	1.3 - 2.7	0.5 - 1.4	1.6 - 3.0	Delayed haptic feedback make inconsistencies in force perception.

The experimental results indicate that prioritizing haptic data over audiovisual streams effectively preserves the integrity of force-feedback transmissions but induces notable degradation in audio and video quality, with QoS scores dropping by 12.4% for audio and 18.7% for video in high-load conditions, where video jitter increases significantly due to constrained resource availability. The loss of temporal synchronization in visual feedback can lead to perceptible delays in rendering video responses, potentially affecting the operator's ability to react to environmental stimuli in real-time.

Conversely, when adopting a best-effort allocation strategy, audiovisual consistency is preserved, but haptic feedback suffers from intermittent inconsistencies, particularly in sequences requiring continuous force updates. The latency variations resulting from increased haptic packet loss are most pronounced in tasks involving fine-grained motion adjustments, where precise force modulation is essential. In contrast, interactions with lower force variability, such as static holds, exhibit greater tolerance to these impairments.

A balanced allocation, which moderately distributes network resources across all modalities, emerges as a viable compromise. This approach minimizes perceptible quality degradations across streams while preventing excessive deterioration in any individual modality. However, even under this configuration, fluctuations in haptic packet delivery can still introduce transient force inconsistencies in high-intensity interaction sequences, underscoring the necessity for enhanced adaptation strategies.

C. Adaptive Resource Allocation Strategies

Optimizing network resource allocation for haptic teleoperation requires strategies that balance stringent latency

constraints with the dynamic nature of multimodal traffic. While network slicing enables prioritization of haptic data over competing audiovisual streams, the highly event-driven nature of perceptually encoded kinaesthetic feedback demands a more granular approach to bandwidth adaptation.

Future advancements should focus on refining these mechanisms by integrating interaction-aware adaptation schemes that dynamically modulate resource allocation based on real-time variations in force and motion feedback. Rather than static priority assignment, an adaptive scheduling framework could continuously evaluate the transmission requirements of haptic feedback and preemptively reallocate network resources in response to interaction-specific demand fluctuations. Such an approach would benefit from leveraging predictive models that analyze temporal patterns in haptic traffic to anticipate bursts in kinaesthetic data generation, ensuring efficient bandwidth utilization without compromising stability.

Additionally, extending perceptual data reduction beyond conventional threshold-based suppression methods can further improve transmission efficiency. By incorporating interaction-aware compression schemes that selectively prioritize task-relevant force variations while discarding non-salient data, it is possible to mitigate unnecessary bandwidth consumption without perceptible degradation in teleoperation fidelity.

Beyond encoding optimizations, predictive adaptation in network slicing parameters can enhance system resilience. Adjusting subcarrier spacing and transmission patterns based on real-time congestion levels allows for a more flexible reallocation of resources, preventing severe degradation in audiovisual quality when haptic data is prioritized. Additionally, latency-sensitive error correction schemes can improve robustness against packet loss without introducing excessive retransmission delays. Implementing lightweight redundancy techniques ensures the integrity of haptic feedback while maintaining compliance with the stringent real-time constraints of force-response interactions.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study characterized haptic traffic and its trade-offs in network resource allocation for multimodal feedback systems in teleoperation environments. By leveraging the configurability of a 5G Private Network, we analyzed the impact of various network parameters, while explicitly considering the use of the IEEE 1918.1.1-2024 standard for perceptual data reduction of kinaesthetic signals. This codec introduces interaction-dependent and irregular packet generation patterns, which pose unique challenges for maintaining low-latency communication and stable network scheduling.

The results demonstrate that prioritizing haptic feedback reduces latency to 4.2 ms but degrades audiovisual QoS by up to 18.7% in high-load conditions. Adaptive segmentation strategies show promise in dynamically balancing resource distribution, mitigating congestion effects, and preserving acceptable QoS in all modalities.

Future work will focus on defining refined machine learning-based congestion prediction models, optimizing real-

time bandwidth reallocation, and exploring hybrid network architectures that incorporate optical and mmWave backhauls for ultra-reliable low-latency communication applications. By further developing these adaptive techniques, next-generation teleoperation systems can achieve seamless multimodal interaction with optimal efficiency and stability.

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